

Prime- Fold Quark Chains as a Source of Energy - 8 Theory

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Abstract:

In this paper, we are going to use the 8 Theory framework to examine An exotic state of prime fold Quark chains in the setting of a varying Lorenz manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. Such a manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. The arbitrary variation term has been discretized and partitioned $\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ to create threefold combination of two distinct elements varying in a. The requirement of threefold is not exclusive and there could be five-fold, seven fold fermion chains.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

We partitioned and discretized the term $\delta g = 0$ and after doing so, allowed the sub element of series to vary as well.

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$\mathbf{0}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0 \quad (1.181)$$

We proved that in order to bring the element back to where it was and to attach it to itself it takes an additional map on the varying element, to a threefold combination.

$$\mathbf{Y}: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1 \quad (1.182)$$

$$\delta g_1(0) \delta g_2(Y) \delta g_1 \quad (1.183)$$

the condition for threefold combination is the simplest one, there is not limitation regarding to it and there could be higher number combinations for $N > 1$.

$$\delta g1(O)\delta g2(Y)\delta g1 \rightarrow 2N + 1 \quad N = 1 \quad (1.184)$$

$$[\delta g1(O)\delta g2\delta g1(O)\delta g2] + (Y)\delta g1 \quad N = 2 \quad (1.185)$$

$$[\delta g1(O)\delta g2\delta g1(O)\delta g2\delta g1(O)\delta g2] + (Y)\delta g1 \quad N = 3 \quad (1.186)$$

We than replace the last element with a terminator, anti-matter, which ensure zero variation, overall:

$$[\delta g1(O)\delta g2\delta g1(O)\delta g2\delta g1(O)\delta g2] + (Y)\delta g\exists 1 \quad (1.187)$$

$$(\delta g1 - (\delta g2 - \delta g1 - \delta g2 - \delta g1 - \delta g2) - \delta g\exists 1) \quad (1.188)$$

$$\delta g1 - chain - \delta g\exists 1 \quad (1.189)$$

If we can somehow destabilize the chain, break it by external source of energy so that the two Elements of matter and anti-matter will meet than we can create a massive outburst of energy.

$$\delta g1 - chain - \delta g\exists 1 + \Delta E = 0 \quad (1.19)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)